

Optimize the Thickness Distribution in Thermoformed Polypropylene/CaCO₃ Composites

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SUMMARY: Thermoforming of polypropylene/CaCO₃ composite sheets has become an important process in industry because of their low cost and good formability. However there are some unsolved problems that confound the overall success of this technique. Nonuniform thickness distribution caused by inappropriate mold design and processing condition is one of them. An L'18 experimental matrix design based on the Taguchi method was conducted to optimize the thermoforming process of CaCO₃ filled polypropylene composites. For the factors selected in the main experiment, the assist plug's displacement and velocity were found to be the principal factors affecting the thickness distribution of thermoformed composites.

KEYWORDS: Thermoforming, polypropylene/CaCO₃ composite, experimental matrix design, Taguchi method

INTRODUCTION

Thermoforming [1,2] of thermoplastic composites has become an important process in industry because of their low cost and good formability. It is most widely used in the packaging industries. Other applications include making large parts such as refrigerator door liners, bathtubs, signs and automotive interior trim. A thick sheet is clamped in a frame and is heated to a temperature well above its glass transition temperature, so that it becomes rubbery and soft. It is then placed over a mold and is stretched to take the contours of the mold, either by plug assist or a differential pressure. The procedure of the thermoforming process is shown schematically in Fig. 1. Thermoforming has advantages over its better known competitor processes such as injection molding and compression molding, because it uses simpler molds and a much lower forming pressure. Thermoforming is the process of choice where short production runs cannot justify the expense of the more expensive injection tooling, or where short lead times from design to production are critical. Larger parts like bathtubs or refrigerator door liners are only economically possible by thermoforming. Although the thermoforming process has been developed for over two decades, there are still some unsolved problems that confound the overall success of this technology.

Nonuniform thickness distribution caused by inappropriate mold design and processing conditions is one of them. During forming, the sheet thins which makes it necessary to optimize the process before molding a part. Conventionally the molders optimize the thickness of thermoformed parts by a time consuming trial-and-error process. Research works [3-15] have been completed in studying the thermoformability of various thermoplastic materials. Only limited effort [16] has been done in optimizing the thermoforming of polymeric sheets.

The goal of this research was to optimize the thickness distribution in the thermoforming of CaCO₃ filled polypropylene composite sheets. An experimental matrix was designed according to the experimental-parameter-design method developed by Taguchi [17-19]. Such an approach allows one statistically and ideally to obtain the same information as a full-factorial experimental design, but with fewer testing trials. The properties obtained from each testing trial are analyzed statistically. In the analysis, a signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio is the statistical quantity representing the power of a response signal divided by the power of the variation in the signal due to noise. The S/N ratio is derived from the loss function and assumes different forms depending on the optimization objectives. The maximization of the S/N ratio leads to the minimization of property sensitive to noise. In order to optimize the thickness distribution of thermoformed polypropylene composites, the following equation describing the nominal-the-best characteristic can be used for the analysis:

$$\eta_i = \frac{S}{N} = 10 \log_{10} \left[\frac{\mu^2}{\delta^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

and,

$$\delta^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \mu)^2 \quad (2)$$

where m is the ideal (target) thickness, y_i is the measured thickness, and n corresponds to the number of samples in each test trial. The optimum factor levels with the largest S/N ratios can then be obtained, which will minimize sensitivity over the range of noises.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The S/N ratios for the thickness distribution were calculated with respect to different points (point 1 to point 6) in the thermoformed parts. The optimum factor levels that could statistically result in the target thickness for different points were predicted to be different. For example, the optimum factor level for point 1 and point 3 were A2/B1/C1/D3/E3 and A3/B1/C2/D4/E1 respectively. These two combinations of factor levels were not identical. Thus, a compromise must be made between the thickness of various points. The best approach was to give a weighted percentage to every point to define its importance. Different Weight percentages were assigned to various points based on their relative significance. We set point 2, 3 and 4 weighted percentages of 25%, 30% and 25%. Point 1, point 5 and point 6 were also assigned weight percentages of 5%, 10% and 5% respectively. The S/N ratio of the measured thickness was then calculated based on the weights of the points. The data of weighted S/N ratio is shown in Fig. 1. The optimum factor levels for the target thickness distribution were thus determined: plug velocity 12 cm/sec, vacuum pressure 0.2 Mpa, heating temperature 160°C, a phenol formaldehyde plug, and plug displacement of 9 cm.

Since the optimum combination of factor level was not included in the main experiment, an indirect route was undertaken to predict the response of the thickness to the optimized factor levels. Assuming there was no interaction among the selected factors, the predicted S/N ratio for the optimized factor levels, $\eta_{A3B1C2D3E1}$, is

$$\begin{aligned}\eta_{A3B1C2D3E1} &= \eta_m + (\eta_{A3} - \eta_m) + (\eta_{B1} - \eta_m) + (\eta_{C2} - \eta_m) + (\eta_{D3} - \eta_m) + (\eta_{E1} - \eta_m) \\ &= \eta_{A3} + \eta_{B1} + \eta_{C2} + \eta_{D3} + \eta_{E1} - 4\eta_m\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

where η_m is the mean S/N ratio for the 18 test trials in the main experiment, and η_{FN} is the S/N ratio for factor F and level N. Based on this equation, the predicted S/N ratio of the thickness for the optimized factor levels, A3/B1/C2/D3/E1, was 22.05 dB. This predicted value was certainly higher than those achieved in the main experiment.

A confirmation experiment was conducted according to the optimized factor levels of A3/B1/C2/D3/E1. The thickness distribution thus obtained is shown in Fig. 2. Additionally, the S/N ratio for this confirmation experiment was 23.09, which was higher than those achieved in the main experiment. Consequently, the target thickness distribution in thermoformed composites was properly reproduced using the optimized factor levels.

The S/N ratio is a rather sensitive indicator that shows that for every three decibel (dB) increase in S/N ratio the error variation is halved relative to the signal [17]. The significance of each factor in the main experiment can be judged by the change of S/N. Based on Fig. 1, the relative significance of each factor on the thickness distribution was arranged in decreasing order of plug displacement ($\Delta S/N=7.59$ dB), plug velocity ($\Delta S/N=6.77$ dB), heating temperature ($\Delta S/N=3.65$ dB), plug material ($\Delta S/N=2.56$ dB) and vacuum pressure ($\Delta S/N=1.86$ dB).

For the factors selected in the main experiment, the plug displacement was found to be the most significant one. The preferred displacement was 9 cm. A smaller displacement tended to increase the thickness at the cup's sides, due to less stretching of the sheet. The second significant factor was found to be the plug velocity. Different velocities resulted in different stretching rates of the composite sheets and thus different thickness distributions. A higher velocity tended to thicken the part's side. Assuming a no slip condition between the sheet and the assist plug, thickness variation caused by different stretching rates is mainly due to the viscoelasticity of the polypropylene composites. The results revealed the viscoelasticity of thermoplastic composites at high temperatures should not be neglected [13,15]. The heating temperature was also found to be a significant factor affecting the final thickness distribution. The optimum heating temperature obtained in this study was found to be 160°C, which matched the value estimated by Malpass et al. [4] using hot tensile tests. The experimental matrix design described here allows one statistically and ideally to obtain the same information as a full-factorial experimental design, but with fewer testing trials. The preferred plug material was found to be phenol formaldehyde. Although the polyoxymethylene (POM) had the lowest thermal diffusivity and kept the sheet at a high temperature for the longest time, an appropriate combination with the other forming factors was even more important to achieve the ideal thickness distribution. Finally the vacuum pressure was found to be insignificant with respect to the thickness distribution of thermoformed polypropylene composites. This suggested that one may use the lowest possible forming pressure to conserve the energy required during the thermoforming process.

CONCLUSIONS

Thermoforming is one of the most important methods to produce hollow plastic articles. The optimization of this process has been essentially based on a time consuming trial-and-error

process. Experimental design based on the Taguchi method was appropriate in optimizing the thickness distribution of thermoformed polypropylene composites by optimizing the processing variables, although there possibly existed experimental error and the correlation amongst the selected factors was neglected in the analysis. For the factors selected in the main experiment, the assist plug's displacement and velocity were found to be the principal factors affecting the thickness distribution of thermoformed composites.

The studies here can be extended by including the following considerations: a). incorporating a thermal effect of the assist plug and mold so that the slip condition between the sheet and the mold can be included, b). considering the material behavior from short fiber filled polymers to long fiber reinforced polymeric composites, and c). extending the plug and mold geometry from the current axisymmetric one to a more general 3-D geometry. These proposed changes will provide a better understanding of the effects of material characteristics and processing conditions on the ideal thickness distribution of thermoformed composites.

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Table 1. Factors and Factor Levels Selected in the Main Experiment

Factors	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
A: Plug Velocity (cm/sec)	8	10	12
B: Vacuum Pressure (Mpa)	0.2	0.25	0.3
C: Sheet Temperature (°C)	150	160	170
D: Plug Material	Wood	POM	Phenol Formaldehyde
E: Plug Displacement (% relative to the maximum displacement of 10 cm)	9 cm (90%)	8 cm (80%)	7 cm (70%)

Figure 1 Variation of the Weighted S/N Ratio for Thermoformed Polypropylene Composite

Figure 2. Comparison of the Target Thickness and the Statistical Result (the solid line is the target thickness and the dash line is the confirmation experiment)

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